

Valuing indigenous and local knowledge in disaster management and nature protection

Recommendations to policymakers to mitigate the negative impacts of Green Deal policies

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The climate crisis requires the participation of all parts of society and all knowledge resources. There is an urgent need to improve disaster prevention and preparation mechanisms, and to mitigate the impact of disasters. Less visible but not less impactful, the biodiversity crisis has also reached critical levels, and it is high time to activate and strengthen the resilience potential of society. Indigenous and local knowledge are essential sources in this process. Until now, the main agents that have produced knowledge and policy guidance for the climate and biodiversity crisis have been intergovernmental bodies and the corresponding national groups; **this set of recommendations argues for a meaningful, systematic, and non-extractive inclusion of the indigenous and local knowledge (ILK) into the structures of knowledge production and their application.** ILK can contribute to both activating disaster management capacities and sustaining functional ecosystems of nature by employing adequate action. The recommendations emphasise the importance of ILK in the design of both local and national policies. For a place-based and regional response, ILK can be of particular importance to the implementation of the policies in the hands of local authorities.

Findings from ACCTING¹

The ACCTING research aims to understand how behavioural change occurs from the perspectives of vulnerable groups. The more specific focus is on what hinders and enables individuals to become more resilient vis-a-vis natural disasters and adapting positive change towards environmental sustainability. 40 narratives relating to disaster management were collected in Italy, Portugal, Sweden, and Turkey; whereas another 50 interviews focusing on nature conservation were conducted in Bulgaria, Hungary, Portugal, Romania, and Turkey. The findings illustrate that **knowledge can be an enabling condition for behavioural change when it comes to disaster management and biodiversity conservation. However, indigenous and local knowledge (ILK) is seldom acknowledged by authorities and the groups holding such invaluable knowledge are rarely part of disaster management structures, or of nature protection organisations.**

Another point emphasized in the interviews is that **policy responses and sound policy implementation are crucial for individuals of vulnerable communities to be able to change their behaviours.** Administrations were identified by interviewees as core actors that should take active roles and incorporate place-based knowledge for stimulating positive change. However, some narratives described by contrast administrations that did not support positive behavioural change. The role of official bodies and the need to incorporate place-based knowledge in their local action has been repeatedly mentioned by our respondents.

Other factors that contribute to behavioural change include **the experience of nature and knowledge cultivated from it; knowledge gained from previous disasters; and solidarity and mutual learning networks.**

¹ Zorell, C., & Strid, S. (eds.) (2023). D3.2 ACCTING Report on first cycle experimental studies. Confidential report delivered to the European Commission 28 April 2023. 281 pages.

Recommendations

1. Administrations and civil society actors in rural regions should **develop long-term relationships with indigenous and local communities**. Long-term relationships based on mutual trust can be crucial for disaster preparation, response, and mitigation. Similarly, this applies to the biodiversity crisis. Building long-term relationships includes the cooperation with active organisations, and working with members from different generations, i.e., the youth and the elderly. Reflecting historical injustices of indigenous and local communities can contribute to establishing a long-term relationship.

2. A true collaboration includes **resource-sharing and providing appropriate financial means** to support initiatives led or guided by indigenous and local communities. Current financing resources are often insignificant as ILK communities are not considered a special target group. Encouraging administrations in charge of disaster and biodiversity challenges for targeted resource-sharing ensures that groups holding ILK receive the necessary support by, for example, extending selection criteria of funding schemes. Integrating ILK in local projects that receive support from regional, national, or EU level sources creates ownership and has the potential to facilitate durable resilience. A process of collaborative goal setting together with the ILK communities can trigger commitments and sustainable effects.

3. ILK can have an immediate and effective contribution to the disaster prevention and mitigation mechanisms through **climate change observation and assessment of future needs**. A local approach where scientists team up with citizens that rarely get a voice can be a game changer. Actively monitoring and understanding the local but also gendered impacts of climate change and the biodiversity crisis can be a starting point for further action. The on-ground understanding can be a trigger for action, e.g. to mitigate risks, improve disaster response, or increase the adaptive capacity of communities in view of the biodiversity crisis.

4. We recommend **recognizing and celebrating positive stories and initiatives** to inspire replication and highlight the success and impact of local community-led efforts. By acknowledging and sharing success stories, we inspire and motivate others to engage in similar initiatives, fostering a culture of innovation and resilience.

5. We recommend a **gender+ sensitive** approach to ILK. Indigenous and local groups often relate to specific gender dynamics, also inherited in their engagements addressing the focus fields of these recommendations. Recognizing the special role of gender dynamics and gender+ inclusivity is an important contribution to sustained action and equal participation. However, traditional role models and gender dynamics often request a critical reflection to activate all knowledge actors.

6. **Active partnerships of concerned administrations with indigenous and local communities** can facilitate the bidirectional exchange of knowledge. Therefore, the capacities of administrations to interact and co-develop with ILK need to be built up, and such efforts need to be recognized positively. Providing access to education, training, and knowledge-sharing to both the communities and the local administrations can facilitate necessary collaboration and unlock respective capabilities. Moreover, it inherits an opportunity to co-evolve and learn from the interaction.

7. In order to trace progress, the policy delivery by administrations should be matched with fitting **monitoring mechanisms to keep track of evidence of successes (and failures)** in the process, especially the collaboration with the vulnerable members of society. Scientists and experts can support with methodological guidance, to keep track of developments and learn from successful, replicable pathways of interaction.

Better Stories

In ACCTING, we look for inspiring bottom-up initiatives as Better Stories, a concept borrowed from Dina Georgis² to refer to promising practices that can instil ideas for how to advance individual and collective behavioural change as envisioned by the Green Deal. The initiatives below are meant as inspiring cases for alternative – and more inclusive – practices where dialogue and mutual learning can take place and where indigenous and local knowledge can impact disaster preparation and nature management processes.

TURKEY

YOLDA INITIATIVE³

Yolda works towards increasing knowledge on the current state and scale of mobile pastoralist communities, their contribution to the ecosystems, and assessing their needs to sustain their livelihoods. Its objective is to learn from them about biodiversity and ecosystems to increase adaptation and resilience to the climate crisis. Yolda conducts scientific research to reveal the connections between mobile pastoralism and its contributions to biodiversity; carrying out advocacy work to support mobile pastoralist groups at national, regional, and global levels; and celebrating their achievements. Yolda closely collaborates with the indigenous nomadic group, Sarıkeçililer. This is one of the mobile pastoralist communities in Turkey which has faced severe challenges in sustaining their livelihood in the last century, particularly in the last recent decades. One of them is the increased access restrictions to their traditional grazing sites. Yolda Initiative supports Sarıkeçililer, in claiming their rights to access their traditional lands and resources and to move freely between summering and wintering grounds, etc.

AUSTRIA

ARCHE NOAH⁴

The association was founded in 1989 on the initiative of gardeners, farmers and journalists who wanted to revalue seeds for farming and nutrition. They underline that since 1900, the diversity of crops has dramatically decreased worldwide – by 75% – due to the industrialization of agriculture. ARCHE NOAH counters this with a positive vision and numerous activities; it preserves and cares for thousands of endangered types of vegetables, fruits, and cereals. ARCHE NOAH is successfully working to bring traditional and rare varieties back into the gardens and onto the market with the support of over 17,000 dedicated members and sponsors. At the intersection of traditional land use,

² Georgis, D. (2013). *The better story: Queer affects from the Middle East*. Suny Press.

³ <https://yolda.org.tr/>

⁴ <https://www.arche-noah.at/>

cultural heritage and traditional food, this initiative contributes to an international network with a dedicated focus on traditional knowledge and sustainable agriculture practice.

BULGARIA

NATIONAL ASSOCIATION OF VOLUNTEERS IN THE REPUBLIC OF BULGARIA⁵ (NADRB)

NADRB successfully coordinates volunteer disaster management efforts in Bulgaria. It has established a working and robust network of national institutions, municipal authorities and formal and informal local volunteer groups that can be swiftly mobilized. It is actively organizing training courses for volunteers in disaster management and recruitment of such groups, predominantly at the local level. In other countries, similar organisations have been established in the past decades, often as an immediate reaction to a disaster (including the crisis related to COVID).

IRELAND

COMMUNITIES 4 CLIMATE ACTION⁶ (C4CA)

C4CA was established in 2019 and has, since then, held several training courses that aim to equip citizens with information on a range of topics including water, waste, procurement, energy, transport, land use, and food. The course is free and open to anyone, hence accessible to a broad range of citizens including vulnerable groups who may not otherwise have access to this type of information and support to get involved in climate action in their communities. Participants have also been inspired to take both individual and collective action in their communities.

GERMANY

QUEICHWIESEN⁷ community of interest

Under the leadership of the Ottersheim municipality, farmers, (nature) conservationists, interested individuals and representatives of municipalities gather since 1996 to practice meadow irrigation. The agricultural cultivation technique of meadow irrigation is based on the sustainable use of the natural resource water. They continue to carry out guided tours and interactive exhibitions to transfer their knowledge to the public. Across Europe, traditional land use techniques are often biodiversity positive and refer to traditional knowledge; in many cases, administrative actors actively contribute to similar initiatives.

⁵ <https://disastermanagement-danube.net/organisations/national-association-of-volunteers-in-the-republic-of-bulgaria/>

⁶ <https://www.esdtraining.net/c4ca>

⁷ <https://queichwiesen.de/>

About ACCTING

ACCTING is an EU-funded project aiming to understand the impact of Green Deal policies on vulnerable groups, prevent inequalities, and produce knowledge and innovations to advance behavioural change at individual and collective levels.

Running until May 2025 and based on two research cycles, ACCTING mobilises research experimentation and innovation to promote an inclusive and socially just European Green Deal, focusing on the inequalities produced by its policies.

Find out more about the project and discover more factsheets at <https://accting.eu>

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Authorship and contributions

Authors: Martin Felix Gajdusek (ZSI), Esin Düzel (SU), Burcu Borhan Türeli (SU), Carina Green (ORU), Carolin Zorell (ORU), Ayşe Gül Altınay (SU), Gábor Szüdi (ZSI).

Contributors: ECSA and contributions from the ACCTING consortium.

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